

Towards Achieving Sustainable Development Goals in Academia: A Case of Good Practice

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Abstract:

Since the adoption of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) program for 2030, achieving sustainable development relies on mobilizing all actors in the territory: the government, local authorities, civil society, but also businesses and the world of education, particularly higher education and research. In this article, we explain how universities are major actors for change in favor of the SDGs and should be considered by other actors as essential partners for achieving them, and how engagement for sustainability should be integrated into the university's activities and decisions. We have adopted a descriptive and comparative approach to explore the meaning given to SDG practices, in light of theoretical declarations and speeches.

At the same time, we examine how universities must also integrate the SDGs into their own operations in order to become one of their main beneficiaries. We illustrate this point with a best practice case study of the Euromed University of Fez, whose design and functioning integrate the SDGs from its creation and explain how its users appropriate them daily in their activities to derive the best benefit.

Using a qualitative analysis approach based on data collection that encompasses all its missions and vocations, we arrive at the result that this university transparently reports on its progress in sustainability and concretely asserts its role as a key actor in its community. In particular, it continuously raises awareness among its stakeholders about the SDGs, supports them through training and communication, and encourages them to adopt responsible and exemplary practices sustainably.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs); Universities Social Responsibility (USR); university; education; teaching; research; innovation; Euromed; FEZ.

Résumé :

Depuis l'adoption par les Nations Unies du programme de développement durable à l'horizon 2030, la réalisation des Objectifs de Développement Durable (ODD) repose sur une mobilisation de l'ensemble des acteurs du territoire : l'Etat, les collectivités territoriales et la société civile bien sûr, mais aussi les entreprises et le monde de l'éducation, l'enseignement supérieur et la recherche en particulier. Dans cet article, nous expliquons en quoi les universités sont des acteurs majeurs du changement en faveur des ODD et doivent être considérées par les autres acteurs comme partenaires essentiels pour leur atteinte, comment l'engagement en faveur de la durabilité doit être intégré dans les activités et les décisions de l'université. Nous avons adopté pour ce faire une approche descriptive et comparative afin d'explorer le sens accordé aux pratiques des ODD, au regard des déclarations et discours théoriques.

Mais en même temps nous examinons comment les universités doivent également intégrer les ODD dans leur propre fonctionnement pour en devenir aussi l'un des principaux bénéficiaires. Nous illustrons ce propos par un cas de bonne pratique ; celui de l'Université Euromed de Fès dont la conception et le mode de fonctionnement intègrent les ODD dès sa création et expliquons comment ses usagers se les approprient quotidiennement dans leurs activités pour en tirer le meilleur bénéfice. Procédant d'une démarche d'analyse qualitative à partir d'une collecte de données, élargie à l'ensemble de ses missions et vocations, nous arrivons au résultat que cette université rend compte de manière transparente de son progrès en matière de durabilité et fait valoir concrètement son rôle d'acteur-clé dans sa communauté. En particulier, elle sensibilise continuellement ses parties prenantes aux ODD, les accompagne par la formation et la communication et les incite à adopter durablement des comportements responsables et des pratiques exemplaires dans ce sens.

Mots clés : Objectifs de développement durable (ODD) ; Responsabilité Sociétale des Universités (RSU) ; université ; éducation ; enseignement et recherche ;

Introduction

The notion of sustainable development appeared in 1987. It is described as development that meets the needs of the present moment, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. The summit of Rio¹ of 1992 formalizes this notion, in particular its 3 pillars: economically efficient, socially equitable and ecologically sustainable development.

In defining sustainable development, one must underline the ethical need not to make development a burden for future generations and to guarantee that their possibilities remain similar to those available to previous generations (Pearce & Atkinson, 1993). That is to say, the cost of societal development should not be imposed on future generations or at least efforts are to be made to compensate for these costs.

This research sheds light on the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their adoption and implementation by Moroccan universities. It highlights the role assigned to universities in such deployment, both as major actors for change in favor of these goals and as primary beneficiaries. The methodology adopted is a descriptive and comparative analysis of the socially responsible university towards the SDGs, emphasizing its environmental, socio-economic, and societal responsibility. The relevant literature associated with sustainability in the university environment is used to support the analysis.

The article emphasizes the awareness of universities regarding the importance of the SDGs as pillars of their own development and that of the country, and supports this assertion through a good practice case study dedicated to a young Moroccan university: Euromed University of Fès. This university integrated sustainability into all stages of its creation and operation.

The qualitative analysis of its infrastructure, missions, and governance, supported by data collection from its components and support functions, is extensively developed in the article, and it concludes that this university has gradually transformed its campus into a place in transition towards social responsibility and sustainability. It fully assumes its role towards its users and territory to contribute to building a more sustainable and just society. Finally, it is starting to benefit from its results by distinguishing itself in international rankings related to the SDGs and its own missions.

¹The Rio Summit is an international conference organized by the United Nations in 1992 to discuss global environmental and sustainable development issues.

In 2015, member states of the United Nations² adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. This 15-year international framework for action aims to create a secure world, free from poverty and famine, promoting full and productive employment, access to quality education and universal health coverage, achieving gender equality, with the empowerment of women and girls, and ending environmental degradation. It is built around an ambitious set of 17 SDGs, summarized below, targeting 169 targets and all of which testify to the scope and ambition of this universal agenda:

1. Eradicate poverty in all its forms everywhere in the world.
2. End hunger, achieve food security, improve nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture.
3. Ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all at all ages.
4. Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.
5. Achieve gender equality and empower women and girls.
6. Guarantee access to water and sanitation for all and ensure sustainable management of water resources.
7. Accelerating access for all to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy.
8. Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all.
9. Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation.
10. Reduce inequalities within and between countries.
11. Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.
12. Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.
13. Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
14. Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.
15. Protect, restore and promote the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainable management of forests, combat desertification and halt and reverse land degradation and biodiversity loss

² *The United Nations (UN) is an international organization established in 1945 after World War II with the aim of maintaining international peace and security, promoting respect for human rights and developing friendly relations among nations.*

16. Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, enable access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels.
17. Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development.

1. The University, driver of change for the SDGs

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development highlights the role of academia in implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It considers higher education institutions to be essential partners, particularly in exploring the many obstacles that could hinder the achievement of these objectives, reviewing the very definition of sustainable development and ensuring the application of its concepts, and formulating an integrated approach that could simultaneously combine social, environmental and economic issues.

Indeed, today's observation is that attempts to integrate these pillars lack efficiency and consistency. Often divergent in fact, priority is first given to social values, then to environmental considerations, both facing strictly economic interests. The latter are therefore only justified insofar as they allow significant social gains.

Additionally, bureaucracy and loose systems slow down any change, and studies have shown that even the most sustainability-driven change agents can face overwhelming bureaucratic hurdles in getting transformational ideas across.

Young people, on the other hand, are better at fighting for the climate and know that to avoid catastrophic damage to the planet and life on it, drastic measures must be taken now to ensure the transition to a society based on development. sustainable. The paradigm shifts to make these measures possible at the university level requires unwavering support and rapid response from all levels of university governance.

The role of the University is essential in the development of a holistic approach that takes into account the convergence between social, environmental and economic issues, all of which must be taken into account to mitigate the difficulties associated with the implementation of the 'Agenda 2030.

The strong involvement of the university in this process and more generally of higher education and scientific research is explicitly recognized in many of the SDGs which also cover a wide range of specific areas such as energy, water and sanitation, industry, agriculture, health, gender equality, the fight against hunger and poverty...

Debates, studies and research carried out by the University on the understanding of sustainable development are essential, on its normative character and the obstacles linked to its realization and will serve as a basis for the definition of the framework allowing, for example, to evaluate if the obligation to promote sustainable development is respected; reduce the degree of uncertainty in these concepts; deconstruct the opposition between economic and social dimensions; promote adaptation to new configurations of the prevailing economic models; reaffirm the need to restructure sustainable development indicators and recognize the centrality of issues related to poverty and inequality.

In the UNESCO World Declaration³ on higher education for the 21st century, it is said that "higher education and research are now essential components of the cultural, socio-economic and ecologically sustainable development of individuals, communities and nations" (UNESCO, 1998). In the final report of its first world conference on higher education for the 21st century, UNESCO defines the main missions of higher education systems: "to educate, train, undertake research and, in particular, contribute to sustainable development and to the improvement of society as a whole", and adds that "the relevance of higher education must be measured by the yardstick of the adequacy between what society expects of institutions and what they do" (UNESCO, 1999).

The university is the place of knowledge and innovation par excellence to support and respond to the challenges of the SDGs, the implementation of which precisely requires new knowledge and ways of proceeding. It is also the place for developing and evaluating practical options to be implemented and for monitoring progress and shaping future young leaders, decision-makers, inventors, entrepreneurs and responsible citizens, equipped with knowledge and skills, passionate and motivated to mark the expected change of the SDGs. Finally, due to its position as a neutral and reliable actor in society, it plays a key role in the education of citizens and mainly other actors.

But at the same time, the university needs to involve itself in achieving the SDGs; if only to demonstrate its ability and willingness to play a significant and decisive role in the development of its immediate or wider environment and its contribution to sustainable development on a

³ UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) is a specialized agency of the United Nations created in 1945. Its purpose is to promote peace and international understanding by encouraging cooperation in the fields of education, science, culture and communication.

global scale. It has the responsibility and the ability to contribute to the achievement of the SDGs, through its practice of university governance, in its transition towards a sustainable university, but also in the accessibility to its spaces and premises and the need to derive party to achieve the SDGs, in the importance of developing student skills and academic research in sustainability and in the necessity and usefulness of monitoring sustainability indicators...

Many universities around the world now speak this same language using the SDGs as a guiding framework. This allows them to promote inter-institutional collaboration and improve their benchmarking comparability. In addition, using the SDGs as a framework means that universities are obligated to address past blind spots, identifiable through mapping their current activities against the SDGs, and then taking action to make them more compatible with the 2030 agenda. In this sense, the role of students is essential because they are endowed with the ability to influence decisions and are incredibly resourceful and motivated to act in favour of the SDGs. Audits are essential to ensure the quality and efficiency of processes and practices in higher education institutions (HEIs), but they must be carried out in a systematic and rigorous way. A seven-step audit process was proposed by the authors and includes planning the audit, collecting information, analysing data, evaluating the results, writing the audit report, presenting results and monitoring of recommendations (Bennouna & Ismaili Alaoui, 2020). It stresses the importance of a participatory approach involving all the actors concerned in the audit, in order to guarantee the credibility and acceptance of the results. Tested in a Moroccan university, this process has proven its usefulness in identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the institution, making recommendations for improving efficiency and performance and its applicability to other institutions in the world. higher education and research.

2. Responsibility of the University in achieving the SDGs

There can be no development that respects the environment, economic viability and social equity, without the real involvement of the education system and in particular higher education. This is all the truer since the fundamental changes necessary to move towards sustainable development begin with individuals, public policies and technological solutions, on their own, being clearly insufficient to achieve this objective.

Due to its multiple missions, some of which interact with its territory, the university is therefore confronted with the question of its own responsibility in achieving the objectives of sustainable development. Indeed, it has the capacity to participate in shaping society with a view to contributing to the SDGs, both from the perspective of its Social Responsibility, Education for

Sustainable Development (ESD⁴) as in its own functioning as an accountable institution. According to (Thöni & Schneller, 2011), universities cannot survive today as self-sufficient systems without direct links to other areas of society. Knowledge and innovation are also known to be important drivers of economic growth, social development and job creation (Harloe & Perry, 2005).

The path towards sustainable development seems inevitable for universities, which have the capacity to shape society and promote socio-economic development. This also implies a responsibility on the part of universities towards their activities and impact on the community and society at large. Beyond legal obligations, universities have a responsibility to adopt responsible practices and promote them to their community and environment in order to transition towards sustainability. This approach should involve three levels of responsibility, aligned with the main pillars of sustainable development: environmental, socio-economic, and societal.

2.1. Environmental responsibility

Environmental responsibility refers to the taking into account by the university of the environmental impact of its activities and services offered and to being interested in improving the living conditions of individuals, with a particular focus on the protection and preservation of natural resources, to meet the needs of present and future generations. Such a responsibility implies for the University to emphasize the themes of the environment and sustainable development, at the level of its programs of study and research-innovation, while functioning as a sustainable community which embodies a behaviour responsible in its consumption of energy, water and other resources (ULSF⁵, 1999). This is how the University must assume its avant-garde role, by innovating and disseminating knowledge around the issues of sustainable development, by raising awareness and training citizens who contribute to the good management of environment and social well-being and by mobilizing other stakeholders around socially responsible actions and projects.

⁴ Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is a concept that aims to promote an understanding of the issues related to sustainable development and to encourage individuals to adopt responsible behavior in terms of development.

⁵ The Urban Landscape Sustainability Framework (ULSF) is a conceptual framework for assessing the sustainability of urban landscapes. It aims to help decision-makers make informed decisions to improve the sustainability of urban landscapes by integrating social, economic and environmental dimensions.

2.2. Socio-economic responsibility

The University brings together students and administrative and teaching staff, with the aim of creating a social bond within this university community. The social dimension of the university's responsibility therefore refers in particular to the commitment of the various actors in community actions, to the integration of aspects of inclusion and equity, social justice, university democracy, citizenship ... which, beyond the legal requirements, impose themselves within this community, invited to constantly question itself on its activities, on the living and study conditions, on its community and territorial anchoring and on its environment socio-economic and natural. Furthermore, as sustainable development becomes an element of economic and territorial competitiveness, new jobs related to the environment, sustainability, and social responsibility are emerging, leading to the development of qualified human resources capable of meeting current and future needs of the region and country in these areas.

2.3. The social responsibility of the University (USR)

The concept of social responsibility is closely linked to that of sustainable development (Nimpaye, Bizimungu & Berthelot, 2021) and involves a voluntary contribution to the challenges of the latter, in activities and their interaction with stakeholders.

(Howard Bowen, 1953), founding father of CSR⁶, calls for what beyond the search for profits, entrepreneurs, businessmen "should try to make their decisions coincide with the objectives of the societal environment in which their business operates, insofar as they should answer for their actions before society" (Diawara & Lavallée, 2014).

The concept then evolved to move out of the business sphere and reach other actors and scales without leading to a real USR strategy.⁷ at the university level. It nevertheless constitutes a framework capable of consolidating the will of any country to integrate social responsibility into its development model and at the level of universities in particular.

Many authors have highlighted the importance of USR for universities, highlighting the benefits for students, universities themselves and society as a whole. Universities that take a USR approach can improve their brand image, attract engaged students and donors, and contribute to important social and environmental causes.

⁶ CSR is a concept that describes how companies integrate social and environmental concerns into their business activities and their relationships with their stakeholders. CSR has two components: ethics and social and environmental performance.

⁷ USR can be ensured through various actions such as research, teaching, relations with local communities, and internal practices in terms of sustainability.

Studies have also shown that students who are exposed to USR programs develop key skills such as critical thinking, problem solving, and leadership, which prepare them to become responsible and engaged citizens. There are different approaches to implementing USR in universities, ranging from setting up student volunteer programs to integrating USR into teaching curricula.

Universities can also collaborate with community partners and non-profit organizations to identify local needs and implement initiatives that meet those needs.

The 2022 survey conducted by the International Association of Universities (IAU) highlights the progress made by universities around the world in implementing the 2030 Agenda. Various aspects of their commitment to sustainability are discussed: their institutional policy for sustainable development and its integration into teaching programs and research, their collaboration with other stakeholders, as well as the challenges and opportunities encountered in the implementation of this agenda (IAU, 2022). This study offers higher education institutions the opportunity to better understand their role in the implementation of the 2030 Agenda, to identify good practices and areas for improvement,

Other similar work highlights the creation of appropriate institutional frameworks within HEIs for sustainability and the systematic integration of sustainability across programs and disciplines, in addition to the development of collaboration among stakeholders. external (Mallow, Tomen & Van't Land, 2020).

For the purposes of better ownership of the SDGs by HEI users, methodological guides propose a four-step approach to accelerate education on the SDGs. This consists of establishing a vision for education for sustainable development (ESD), assessing its current state, developing an action plan and measuring progress (SDSN, 2020). Concrete examples of good practice are presented as well as resources to help schools implement ESD.

Similarly, academic bodies propose a similar three-step approach to integrating the SDGs into HEI activities, which consists of three steps: establishing an action plan, mobilizing and engaging stakeholders, then implementing and evaluating progress. The document provides practical cases of practice of the SDGs in international institutions, as well as support materials for their integration into teaching and research.

3. The Moroccan University facing sustainable development

With regard to Morocco, despite the great dynamics of societal changes which are pushing the higher education system to find its place to respond to contemporary challenges, it is clear that

a large number of universities still escape this important international dynamic. (Lefdaoui & Khohmimidi, 2015). The reading of the Moroccan university context says a lot about the insufficiency of past experiences in terms of reconciliation of the university with its environment, and seems to reflect many gaps between the university offer and the various societal changes present (Bakhella WJ, 2022).

This discrepancy between Morocco's political commitments for sustainable development and the practices of Moroccan universities, as well as the urgency that the Moroccan university is now part of the dynamics of sustainability by pairing them with the territory, calls into question the reflection and the action around the theme of USR in Morocco, to grasp its aims and explore more closely the university commitment in its favour, particularly in terms of teaching and research, but also in terms of construction and development of campus and student life.

It is, however, remarkable that THE Impact Ranking, which is based on the SDGs, is attracting more and more Moroccan universities with encouraging results.

This is how, recently, Moroccan universities have become increasingly involved in the implementation of the SDGs, within them and on their territories, in perfect synergy with the national SDG-2030 plan drawn up by the Moroccan government and monitored by the High Commission for Planning.

The reports of the High Commission for Planning underline significant progress made by Morocco in the implementation of the SDGs but nevertheless note significant challenges that still remain to be addressed, particularly with regard to poverty, inequality, access to drinking water and sanitation, quality of education, health and climate change (HCP, 2021).

Recommendations for an integrated and inclusive approach are highlighted, involving stakeholders at all levels and highlighting the need to improve coordination and governance as well as strengthening institutional capacities and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. Access also emphasizes the importance of mobilizing financial resources to accelerate the implementation process, in particular by encouraging private investment in sustainable projects and mobilizing international financing (HCP, 2020).

In terms of energy, the old campuses and university residences are moving towards more energy efficiency, in particular by setting up optimized energy systems with the use of photovoltaic panels which are becoming widespread, but also by a set of individual actions to inform and raise awareness among users.

Sustainability has also become a priority for new buildings (HQE standard) and the concept of eco-campus or green university is highlighted in the development of specifications. This mainly concerns energy and the energy efficiency of buildings, water consumption and recycling, waste collection and treatment; and more broadly mobility on campuses and the use of electric vehicles, dematerialization and its carbon impact on supplies, purchases and consumption of paper, etc.

The importance of the social responsibility of Moroccan universities, in the context of the COVID19 pandemic, was particularly highlighted and concrete measures were taken to improve their commitment to educational continuity and equity of access to resources, in promoting diversity and inclusion, in reducing environmental impact on university campuses, and in community engagement and strengthening their relationships with local partners, in times of crisis (UAE, 2022).

4. Case of good practice: action of the Euromed University of Fez (UEMF) for the SDGs

The creation of the UEMF emanates from the Initiative of the King of Morocco, with the desire to create in Fez a higher education and research framework based on intercultural dialogue, exchange and cooperation between the two shores of the Mediterranean, with a natural extension to Sub-Saharan Africa, while offering excellent training and conducting very high-level scientific research in close connection with the socio-economic world.

It thus sets itself up as a training and research university that promotes the three cycles of university training and its training programs, in perfect harmony with the SDGs, aim to give graduates a strong employability potential; but also of entrepreneurship to create start-ups and spinoffs themselves. It also conducts high-level research that meets the needs of society and aims to be one of the major drivers of regional development and leaders in digital transformation, innovation and entrepreneurship.

Wishing to embody this role and fully invest in this approach, the UEMF has chosen to invest in the establishment of a collective reflection around the integration of sustainable development and social responsibility issues by all its actors and partners.

Indeed, the University has been committed for more than 10 years to sustainable development and socio-ecological transition through its approach inspired by the strategic vision established from its conception.

Thanks to the action of all its services, laboratories and educational components, the University obtained in 2021 the labels relating to "Sustainable Development and Social Responsibility",

thus placing it among the Moroccan universities most committed to of the socio-ecological transition. These labels now encourage the university to engage in a process of continuous improvement with regard to the integration of transition issues in its research and training missions as well as in its activities related to student life on its campus.

4.1. The SDGs at the heart of UEMF's strategic vision

Among the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Goal 4 focuses on quality education and its target 4.3 specifically deals with equity in higher education aimed, by 2030, at ensuring equal access for all women and men to affordable and quality higher education. Even if this target naturally arouses its interest, the Euromed University of Fez unreservedly supports the progress towards all the objectives and implements the most adequate framework to concretize them, with the adoption of new practices and the decision-making accelerating the various transitions: from goals related to poverty (SDG1), health and well-being (SDG 3), gender equality (SDG5), governance, decent work and economic growth (SDG 8). The question of university performance, in its broadest sense, emanates from the strategic vision of development drawn up by the university; then broken down into thematic, assessable and measurable action plans, using performance indicators.

The implementation of an SDG-oriented strategy is easier to implement if it accompanies the genesis of a university project from the outset and this is precisely the case of the UEMF whose very conception of the eco-campus foreshadows an approach that takes into account the priority areas of a green university. These are constructions, energy, waste and its collection, water and its recycling, mobility and social responsibility, digitization and dematerialization reducing consumption to a strict minimum. of paper, etc.

The leadership of the Chairman and the consistency of actions by the management team are at the heart of the implementation of such a strategy and their individual and collective commitment, at the highest level of management, in the concretization of action plans in favour of the SDGs are a pledge of ownership of its plans by all components and users of the university. The latter's ability to sustainably deploy progress actions is thus strengthened. (see Figure N°1).

Figure N°1: UEMF strategic vision in favour of the SDGs and its translation into actions

Source: Author

4.2. Breakdown of the strategy into action plans

4.2.1. Infrastructure

Resolutely in line with a policy of setting an example in terms of sustainable development, the construction of the UEMF campus has set four priorities: its integration into the site; water and energy management; durability and ease of maintenance; comfort and health. The performance levels set also take into account the objectives of respecting costs and flexibility.

Apart from the heritage policy in terms of environmental performance, the UEMF eco-campus also aims to develop social and economic orientations in accordance with sustainable development: choice of research themes developed and potential for technology transfer to be disseminated on the territory and to create jobs locally, integration into surrounding neighbourhoods (student life, shared facilities, jobs and services), diversity of populations, uses and activities, etc.

For constructions, the buildings made both in the choice of materials and in the design of spaces and circulations, are energy efficient and integrate renewable energies while remaining in accordance with international standards of comfort. The outdoor spaces have been laid out with particular attention paid to the limitation of waterproofing (parking and roads), infiltration and storage of rainwater and runoff on site (ditches, basins, draining pavements), plantations (woody, shrubs, lawn) whose needs in water, phytosanitary treatment and fertilization are limited as well as lighting and atmospheres.

4.2.1.1. Energy

The UEMF aims to maintain optimized energy systems in the medium term, both through a set of individual awareness and action measures and through an increasingly efficient energy management process, reconciling energy efficiency and diversification of energy sources, particularly renewables, as well as the widespread use of LED lighting. In the longer term, the university expects each component to be able to assess its own energy consumption and highlight its own energy saving potential as a notable progress action in its budget.

4.2.1.2. Water

Located in a geographical area with low rainfall, aggravated in recent years by significant climate change, particularly in this region of the world, the University scrupulously ensures that its water consumption is constantly monitored and reduced. Gray water circuits are provided to use drinking water only when necessary. Similarly, water-saving taps are fitted to all of the

buildings and sanitary facilities, and inspection and monitoring rounds are carried out daily against water leaks and unnecessary waste.

4.2.1.3. Waste and its collection

Sustainable waste treatment always starts with optimized collection, cardboard, paper, plastic and metal are separated in the corridors and floors of the campus. Their optimized flow and recovery reduce day-to-day waste, supported by awareness-raising visuals for all users, who willingly comply with selective sorting.

Being an eco-campus connected with a few kilometres of fibre optics, digitization and dematerialization, reinforced by the COVID 19 crisis, have resulted in an annual saving of several tons of paper. The same goes for tendering procedures, for construction or the purchase of equipment and supplies, now digitized as much as possible and which significantly reduce the use of paper, ink cartridges and postal services and thus considerably limit unnecessary waste.

4.2.1.4. Mobility

The eco-campus has also been designed so that CO₂ emissions due to transport are very low. Upon accessing the site, the motorist must of course park his vehicle, the parking areas being located on the outskirts of the buildings.

Traffic in and between the buildings is necessarily pedestrian and largely accessible to people with reduced mobility. For longer trips, a green mobility system has been set up using clean vehicles placed at different points on campus: electric cars, e-scooters, e-scooters... This ecological project was carried out by a start-up set up by young graduates and incubated at the University.

In addition, a restricted mobility policy on campus is now strongly encouraged, made possible thanks to digital technology and accelerated by the COVID 19 pandemic, making work, exchange, coordination and training less dependent on location and time.

4.2.2. Social and societal responsibility (RSS)

Beyond these concrete actions related to the physical space and its use, the UEMF places the following principles and values at the heart of its mode of operation; a university:

- open to the world and promotes the values of inclusion, moderation, tolerance, interculturality and sharing;
- open to all students and staff, national and international, without discrimination based on origin, family situation, gender, disability or creed;

- which advocates equal chances and opportunities, gender equality and implements a proactive policy to include a maximum number of women as well as people with reduced faculties;
- which recognizes and rewards excellence following an evaluation at all levels, both top-down and bottom-up;
- which promotes critical thinking, rationality, citizenship values based on good citizenship, civility, commitment, sense of duty and common interest as well as respect for others and the environment;
- which encourages the qualities of initiative, entrepreneurship, innovation-creation and mastery of languages and cultures;
- which has a social responsibility and offers tuition, accommodation and catering scholarships to the best students from low-income families and from Sub-Saharan Africa.

These principles and values, most of which are consistent with the SDGs, are translated into policies and translated into charters and action plans.

In terms of Social and Societal Responsibility, the Euromed University of Fez is not limited only to the training of high-level graduates. It also emphasizes the training of citizens imbued with the values of living together, otherness and critical thinking, aware of their duties and rights and responsible for the protection of the environment and respect for others and of nature.

To do this, the mobilization of its actors around its RSS policy mainly concerns the issues of parity, pay equity and the inclusion of disadvantaged people, the disabled and immigrants, the commitment against discrimination, the work of children, forced labour and human trafficking, support and benevolence towards motherhood and paternity, non-discrimination against women and the fight against all types of harassment, solidarity towards people and disadvantaged neighbourhoods as well as good environmental management for a sustainable campus.

In this regard, the gender equality charters of the Euromed University of Fez, social responsibility and the code of ethics and professional conduct guide the actions carried out every day on campus to implement this RSS policy.

The University has set itself the objective of achieving and maintaining gender parity, using positive discrimination in the event of equality of profiles and skills; by integrating a maximum of people with reduced physical abilities and people with an immigrant background (university USR charter, 2022).

The UEMF is also a member of an international network of universities implementing an action plan “Equality between Women and Men”

Wanting to be accessible to all, the Euromed University of Fez has set up an innovative equity access system for its users which promotes excellence, while granting diversified scholarships to students from the most disadvantaged backgrounds and especially girls from rural areas, with full coverage of school fees, accommodation costs and catering costs. Support for students in difficulty or with disabilities is also provided.

In addition, an incentive remuneration system is not saturated to encourage applications from women in fields where they are under-represented (artificial intelligence, mechanical engineering, civil engineering, management positions, etc.). An "Equality and Equity" committee is set up at the level of the University Presidency to make continuous improvements concerning the Equal Opportunities and Equity policy, to implement it and to monitor and audit of its application (university USR policy, 2022).

To banish any discrimination based on social rank, gender, sexual orientation, creed, age, ethnic origin, immigration status or disability, the University works for the development of its community by cultivating a sense of belonging and by making available all the means and working conditions to create a stimulating, serene climate conducive to innovation, creation and creativity.

4.2.3. Governance

The University has built its governance system on transparency, integrity, bottom-up and top-down evaluation, performance management and improvement, and accountability. Its governance can be illustrated by the following conceptual diagram (see Figure N°2).

Figure N°2: Conceptual diagram of university governance for the achievement of the SDGs

Source: Author

The SDGs that it accomplishes are all the more achievable since their realization is an emanation from its highest decision-making body: The Board of Directors, which adopts the strategy, over the medium and long term. This is then translated into operational action plans, concerted and consolidated by the executive bodies (faculties and departments), including the communication and awareness plan to be rolled out to all users; essential relays for the implementation of the actions decided upon. The communication emphasizes the direct impact of achieving the SDGs on the quality of life of users on campus, but also on their contribution to the preservation of heritage and the environment and the extremely positive spin-offs that this arouses among citizens and the entire community.

For all meticulously carried out actions in favour of sustainable development, data is carefully collected and stored using the UEMF information system. A system implemented for more than four years which is mainly based on the ERP KONOSYS, designed on the basis of a specific configuration notebook produced by the entities of the University and validated jointly. It covers the following 6 modules whose processes are now completely computerized and dematerialized: education, human resources management, heritage, research, the E-learning platform and the quality management system; with a consolidated and secure database. In addition, the information system is connected to the SAGE 1000 financial suite for all accounting and management operations.

The data provided by the information system (IS), including those relating to actions related to the SDGs for teaching, research-innovation, governance and actions carried out by student clubs in favour of the community are analysed and then restructured into dashboards. The same applies to the data collected by the audit, quality assurance and evaluation departments, collected as part of monitoring the execution of actions.

Dashboards constitute a valuable base of knowledge and decision support, from which lessons are drawn from the monitoring of operations and improvement actions are identified accordingly, to be reported for the purposes of revision or improvement. adjustment, to the executive team when they concern the operational aspect; even higher when they concern the strategic aspect.

This conceptual scheme of university governance in favour of the SDGs appeals by its dynamic nature which allows meticulous monitoring of projects, facilitated by an IS which includes all the processes defined in the quality management system of the University. The latter incorporates a 360° assessment scheme which includes, in addition to self-assessment,

ascending, descending and cross-sectional internal assessments, as well as external assessment entrusted to third parties. Internal evaluations also include student evaluation of teaching and teaching as well as that of the “quality assurance and control” process.

4.2.4. Education

The teaching offer of the University is today structured in three poles: the "Engineering and architecture" pole with 3 components, the "Human and Social Sciences" pole with 3 components and the "Health" pole with 3 components including one Faculty of Medicine which opens its doors in September 2023 (see Figure N°3).

Figure N°3: UEMF pedagogical architecture

Source: UEMF

The University has implemented a proactive student aid policy in the form of tuition, catering, accommodation or mobility grants, with special support for students in difficulty or with disabilities. Today 50% of students benefit from this policy which makes the university accessible to all, regardless of their origins or their social level.

Citizenship education takes the form of a cross-curricular pedagogical base that is compulsory and generalized to all university courses, whatever their nature (cf. Figure N°4). This base which defines the Euromed profile, a specificity specific to the UEMF and forming part of its DNA, is composed of the following 7 pillars:

1. Multilingualism
2. Multiculturalism,
3. Entrepreneurship,
4. International mobility,
5. Mastery of new information and communication technologies,
6. Eco-citizenship,
7. Social Responsibility.

Figure N°4: Euromed profile and its 7 pillars: compulsory training base for all students

Multilingualism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compulsory and perfect command of both languages, English and French, as well as a third language of the Euro-Mediterranean area.
Multiculturalism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • generalized teachings and conferences on History, civilizations, Euro-Mediterranean heritage, Philosophy and Critical Thinking.
Entrepreneurship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • development of initiative, innovation and creation, through teaching, internships and Hackathons supervised by professors and experts from socio-economic backgrounds.
International mobility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • academic stays abroad and in Euro-Mediterranean partner institutions.
Mastery of ICT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital and multimedia environment, demanding and forward-looking.
Eco-citizenship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness and mobilization for sustainable development and environmental issues in the form of courses, seminars, conferences of field actions.
Social responsibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • projects, para-educational activities or internships of a social nature.

Source: UEMF

University training is not to be outdone: several masters deal with issues of energy (renewable energies and energy efficiency, design and engineering of green buildings), water, the environment and mobility. Architecture, design or civil engineering courses give an important place to sustainability, particularly in eco-design and the choice of building materials. Training in digital engineering and artificial intelligence also focuses, through student projects, on the impact of digital transformation on ecology, energy, agriculture, industry, transport and medicine; but also tourism, culture, heritage, etc.

The University promotes pedagogical innovation for all its courses by generalizing the skills-based approach and proceeding from an active pedagogy by project which generates learning through the realization of a concrete production. This teaching model where the project is at the heart of the training system cognitively engages learners to question the resources to be developed in order to encourage the search for solutions. They thus acquire knowledge and skills through experience, conducive to the development of know-how and skills and to the strengthening of their autonomy and their communication and collaboration skills.

Conversely, the University has been deploying for years the evaluation of teaching and teachers by its students. Each teacher provides his students at the beginning of the year with the detailed syllabus of the course for which he is responsible, setting its objectives, its organization, its pedagogy, its bibliographical references, its methods of evaluation, the regulations in force in addition to other additional practical information. This document acting as a contract between the teacher and his students, the latter participate twice a year, at the end of each semester, in an anonymous and remote evaluation survey, by answering a dozen questions, both on teaching

itself than on the person responsible for it. A way to assess to what extent said contract is validly fulfilled, both on the content of the course and on the teaching methodologies and tools useful by the teacher and on his behaviour. This exhaustive evaluation since it concerns all students, all teachers and all courses without exception, is seen more as a means of continuous improvement of engineering and teaching delivery than as a control and is now a valued tradition. both by the learners and by their trainers.

4.2.5. Research

University research is partly oriented towards the SDGs thanks to its teams specializing in renewable energies, energy efficiency, bio-sourced materials, robust and light materials for aeronautics, and green hydrogen. Other laboratories work on sustainable development, water desalination and renewable energies, including an on-campus house for studies and research on energy efficiency. Some of these themes are mentioned as follows:

- In engineering sciences:

Environmental Engineering; renewable energies; desalination and water treatment; functional materials and nanomaterials; bioceramics; hybrid materials for insulation; improved local materials for construction; low-energy buildings; artificial intelligence; data science & big-data; cyber-security; additive manufacturing; medicinal chemistry; biomedical genius; biotechnology; mobility and vehicles of the future; aeronautics; civil engineering and urban mobility;

- In the humanities and social sciences

Euro-Mediterranean history, civilizations and heritage; Euro-Mediterranean spaces, territories and societies; neighbourhood policies and regional integration; architecture, town planning and heritage; issues of the Euromed area (migration, security, transport, youth work, trade, etc.)

Several high-level technological platforms in different fields are pooled between the components: additive manufacturing (3D) and prototyping, process engineering and civil engineering, materials synthesis and characterization, biotechnology and biomedical engineering, renewable energies storage and energy efficiency, engineering digital and artificial intelligence. They are used for training by and for research and also to conduct partnership research and to imagine, design and develop new devices, processes and products with the objective of technology transfer to the national private sector or the creation of new start-ups and spinouts.

They are also made available to partner universities, in particular those of the Fez-Meknes Region and national ones, and also to companies to support them in their innovation strategies and to strengthen their competitiveness in the face of a very competitive international environment.

Innovation and development structures are also backed by these platforms to consolidate an ecosystem conducive to innovation and R&D, in areas associated with the SDGs in particular:

- Agro Energy TIC Valley (mixed platform for testing, research and training in the fields of bioenergy and energy storage,
- Fez Smart Factory (space for the development of industrial activities with productivity improved by the concepts and tools of industry 4.0⁸, backed by a 4.0 factory)
- Agritech (pole for the emergence of the insufficiently exploited potential of the Fez-Meknes region in its traditional activities (agriculture and agri-food) and the development of territorial growth relays that create wealth and jobs
- UEMF Innovation Center (incubator for start-ups and support for project leaders, with high innovation potential)

4.2.6. Partnership

For the realization of these technological platforms and innovation spaces, the University relies on a network of national and international partners that it has been able to develop over the years and with which it has been able to establish notoriety and credibility, based on both trust and performance.

Thus, a Climate Center is being set up at the UEMF, in collaboration with the Union for the Mediterranean⁹ and the installation of the aforementioned Factory 4.0, with a large component concerning innovation in energy efficiency, reinforces this dynamic.

At the local, regional and national levels, the University participates in the development of policies aimed at achieving Morocco's international commitments for sustainable development and clean energies. It also offers its services to local industries to improve their energy

⁸ Industry 4.0, also known as the "Fourth Industrial Revolution", refers to the use of advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and data analytics to improve production processes and supply chains.

⁹ The Union for the Mediterranean (UfM) is an intergovernmental organization created in 2008 to strengthen cooperation between the countries bordering the Mediterranean in the economic, social and environmental fields.

efficiency, raises awareness and assists communities, through training and mentoring, able to support the start-up of sustainable businesses.

4.3. Benchmarking and continuous improvement

In order to measure its performance and its processes, to identify opportunities for internal improvement and to obtain enough information to access the best operational practices, the University has decided to use Benchmarking, a practice that is now universally acclaimed. by organizations to secure and maintain their advantage. Already labelled Eco-campus in 2016, by COP 22 in Marrakech, the UEMF participates each year in international university competitions and rankings, particularly those related to the SDGs.

For its first participation in the world ranking “Time Higher Education¹⁰Impact Rankings 2022” concerned 1406 universities in 106 countries and regions, the Euromed University of Fez was ranked first in its region and fourth nationally. The detailed analysis of this ranking places it, at the level of Morocco, in first place for SDGs 1, 2, 5, 10 and 12; ranked second for SDGs 8, 9 and 17 and third for SDG4. UEMF has applied for THE impact Rankings 2023. A general report and a report by SDGs are written and updated periodically on the university website.

The UEMF also distinguished itself in 2022 as the first Moroccan university in the world ranking of universities “U-Multirank¹¹2022”. This global ranking is based on a multidimensional analysis of higher education institutions around the world. The aim is to distinguish the best performances in terms of teaching and learning, research, knowledge transfer, international openness and regional commitment.

In the previous ranking “U-Multirank 2021”, three Moroccan universities were positioned in the top 10 of African universities and among them the Euromed University of Fez (UEMF), ranked second and placed in the top 25 worldwide for the criterion of international student mobility.

The Responsible Innovation label set up by the Agence Universitaire de la Francophonie (AUF) and awarded to higher education and research institutions, has the dual objective of mapping and promoting responsible innovations from French-speaking universities around the world, but also deploying the responsible innovation network to promote synergies between universities, civil society and the socio-economic sector working for the development of a

¹⁰ Time Higher Education (THE) is a British higher education magazine that publishes world university rankings. ¹¹U-Multirank is a European university ranking system which was launched in 2014. It is funded by the European Commission and is managed by a consortium of academic and research organisations.

responsible society. For its first edition 2020/2021, the Euromed University of Fez has won this label for its project entitled "Sustainable UEMF Program".

Moreover, during a ceremony organized in Paris on October 4, 2022 and chaired by the Minister of Higher Education and Research of the French Government, the Euromed University of Fez was named winner of the "Responsible campus of the year", rewarded for its commitment to the SDGs, to becoming a responsible organization vis-à-vis the challenges of transition, in the following four areas:

- Leadership and governance;
- Real Estate and Operations;
- Learning, teaching and research;
- Partnership and commitment.

Likewise, the UEMF is among the list of 56 finalist universities, representing 19 countries around the world, for "The Green Gown Award" which recognizes outstanding sustainability initiatives undertaken by universities and colleges around the world. This award is organized in partnership with the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and supported by the AUF, the Association of Commonwealth Universities (ACU) and the International Association of Universities (IAU).

UEMF was the winner of the first edition of the international prize "ZAIRI International Awards for Excellence in Higher Education for excellence in higher education", inaugural edition 2022, in the "Digital Transformation" category.

The inaugural 2022 edition which received nominations from universities representing 31 countries wants this annual international award to be given to honour higher education institutions that strongly impact their own context, embracing excellence and innovation in specific areas relevant to digital transformation, research impact, community service, among others. Finally, the UEMF is the only university in Morocco to win the "Certificate of Excellence" for its Gender Equality Strategy, as part of the "Professional Equality" Trophy.

4.4. Contributions of the University for the achievement of the SDGs and targeted targets:

Due to its comprehensiveness, we prefer to summarize this contribution in the form of the following summary table (see Table N°1):

Table N°1: Contributions of the University for the achievement of the SDGs and targeted targets

		University missions			
Main SDG targets	Main goals	Education	Research	Governance	Community Service
Planet	Fight against the degradation of the planet	<p>Raising awareness and training open to students and external users on climate change, water management and energy efficiency, sustainable transport and mobility, ecoconstruction and eco-materials.</p> <p>Examples of sectors targeting the SDGs: <u>Masters:</u> Renewable energies and energy efficiency, design and engineering of green buildings, environmental</p>	<p>Priority research themes in relation to the SDGs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable energies and energy efficiency • Materials, Nanomaterials and Additive Manufacturing • Vehicles and land mobility • Aeronautics and aerospace 	<p>Reduction of the carbon footprint by the dematerialization of energyintensive tasks in paper and toners: handouts, examinations, calls for tenders, and use of the information system for all management, coordination, evaluation and steering activities.</p>	<p>Eco-campus combining energy saving and energy efficiency, water saving and its recycling, intramural green mobility and accessibility for people with reduced mobility.</p> <p>Raising awareness and actions of student clubs Clubs in favor of protecting the planet:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Hackathons:</u> AI applied to eco-mobility; Student's Innov-Up; Euromed

	<p>engineering and water management, sustainable transport and mobility, functional materials and additive manufacturing</p> <p><u>Engineering and architecture;</u></p> <p>civil engineering, design, architecture, digital engineering and artificial intelligence</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • environmental engineering • medicinal chemistry • Biotechnology and Biomedical Engineering • Civil Engineering and Urban Mobility 	<p>Policies:</p> <p>responsible purchasing, stakeholder identification, responsible digital, smoke-free campus</p> <p>Transparency: display of SDG policies and reports on the website</p>	<p>Sustainable Impact Challenge; GreenWings: carpooling, catering, eco-scoring and eco-ranking.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Workshops:</u> Migration, mobility and development; Project as Caring - Making as Healing • Incubators and FSF: creation of startups and support for responsible companies for industry 4.0
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<p>Population</p>	<p>Eradicate poverty and hunger, ensure dignified living conditions and guarantee equity and equality</p>	<p>Parity largely achieved between students (54% of students are girls) Granting of merit and excellence scholarships covering all or part of tuition fees, in particular for deserving young people from disadvantaged backgrounds (40% of scholarship students) Granting of doctoral scholarships in favor of brilliant Bac+5 graduates as a way of deploying the doctoral cycle (95% of doctoral students are scholarship holders). Deployment of the Euromed profile: a transversal and compulsory training base for all based on 7 pillars all</p>	<p>UEMF: member of the international consortium for gender equality Encouragement of female graduates to do a doctoral cycle Research themes in the humanities and social sciences promoting gender equity and equality: Tourism and heritage; Ancient architectures and heritage; Mobilities in the Euromed space; Identities, mobilization, political participation in the Euromed space; migration;</p>	<p>Equal visibility, autonomy, responsibility and participation of both sexes in all spheres of university life” Gender equality in terms of access to employment, training, mobility, promotion and equal pay. Equity and inclusion of disadvantaged or disabled people and immigrants Daily fight against all forms of discrimination related to gender, ethnic and social origins, language, religion or</p>	<p>A welcoming framework for students, dignified and respectful of equality and equity. Inclusion and solidarity scholarships for students from disadvantaged backgrounds that cover their accommodation and/or catering costs and guarantee fair chances of success (17% of students benefit from this type of scholarship) Particular attention to students with specific needs and girls from very modest backgrounds. Solidarity and support actions carried out by student clubs in favor of the inhabitants of disadvantaged</p>
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		<p>oriented towards the SDGs: Multilingualism, interculturality, ICT, entrepreneurship, mobility, social responsibility, sustainable development.</p> <p>Annual training cycles (Soft and Professional Skills) for elected representatives of the Region and executives of municipal services.</p> <p>Support in training and setting up income-generating projects for young unemployed graduates.</p>	<p>Urbanization and development of industry; Actions undertaken within the framework of the chair: “Women in Science”</p>	<p>beliefs, opinions, disability, age, etc. Positive discrimination for equal profiles and skills, priority for women for recruitment (among the academic and administrative staff, 51% are women)</p>	<p>neighborhoods or rural areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ Warm winter (Rotaract club); • Medical caravan for the population of the province of Boulemane; • Citizen action for the Farfara school; • Cleaning and embellishment in a district of the industrial zone ...
Prosperity	<p>Reconciling economic and social progress with respect for nature</p>	<p>Reinforcement of the digitization and dematerialization of teaching and teaching materials.</p>	<p>Structuring projects in research and innovation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agirtech • EnergyTIC 		<p>Activities of student clubs coached by professors and professionals aimed at the development of economic and social projects that</p>

	<p>Development of self-training and distance learning.</p> <p>Highlighting the role of digital and AI in engineering and architecture training; adoption of the skills-based approach and project-based teaching: projects carried out by students aimed at optimizing resources and reducing the carbon footprint in the economic and social sectors.</p> <p>Certifying and diploma training actions in favor of companies aiming at these objectives: the case of ALTEN, CGI, CRI, etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fes Smart Factory • Technology platforms • 3D digital platforms experience • 3D printing platform • Renewable energies platform <p>Support for the Region through impact studies and advice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital diagram of the Region • Regional Continuing 	<p>respect nature. Examples of Hackatons carried out with RAM, CRI and AWB, WebHelp, Bank of Africa...</p>
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			Education Master Plan		
Peace	Promote peace and justice	<p>Participation of the University in the biannual Mediterranean sessions of advanced strategic studies 5+5 organized by the FEMS</p> <p>Organization by the UEMF of the May 2022 session on the theme: "Challenges, risks and opportunities common to both shores of the Mediterranean"</p>	<p>Hosting by the UEMF of the 9th United Nations World Forum on the Alliance of Civilizations: 300 young people representing 98 nationalities, divided into several groups, discussed interreligious dialogue, the fight against discrimination and intolerance, the promotion of peace through sport, the role of education and women for a just, peaceful and more inclusive society...</p>	Establishment of the function of Mediator	Actions of student clubs in favor of more justice and social peace

Partnership	Establish effective and inclusive partnerships to achieve the SDGs	Partnerships with several universities and schools in the Euromed area (Spain, Italy, Portugal, France, Belgium, Sweden, etc.) to promote student and teacher mobility as well as double degrees.	Strong and structuring partnership with the industrial community for funded research & innovation projects: Thales, Safran, Iresen, Elephant Vert, Alten, Sunomix, PSA, Huawei, etc.	Strong involvement of personalities from the economic, political, social and cultural sectors in all decision-making bodies of the University: □ Board of Directors · University Council · Scientific Advice Councils of Establishment	Fruitful and lasting partnerships in favor of the reception of students in internships and the integration of graduates. Support for the incubation of projects led by young people within the UEMF Innovation Center and its platforms Helping industrialists wishing to operate their digital transformation to take advantage of the Fes Smart Factory Project and its 4.0 factory
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Source: Author

Conclusion

In this article, we have tried to highlight the essential role of universities, both as major players in the implementation of the SDGs, in favour of citizens and institutions, but also as their own beneficiaries of the appropriation of these SDGs by their users, in the daily exercise of their teaching, research and openness to their environment.

University leaders, professors, administrators and students must all participate, in particular through the implementation of concrete solutions in sustainable development and tangible activities, supported by the commitment of the components and the involvement of its "student clubs". which aim to prepare them throughout life to meet the challenges of the 21st century. More than ever, collaborative research and open science are essential to contribute to the recovery and resilience of societies, by linking education to other sectors such as health, employment or the environment. This is why the circulation of knowledge and research between education systems remains essential.

The practical case of the Euromed University of Fez is no exception to this rule. Through its research, teaching and learning activities, its state-of-the-art facilities, its leadership and the strong involvement of its young people, all of whom are particularly sensitive to issues of sustainability and the protection of the environment, such a commitment is advantageous for the university. It allows it to unequivocally demonstrate the economic and social benefits of achieving these goals, to take advantage of the demand for educational content related to the SDGs, to establish new partnerships, to obtain new sources of funding and to define itself as a university endowed with both a conscience and a social responsibility.

Faced with the global social and environmental emergency, accentuated by the covid-19 pandemic, the UEMF is contributing its stone to the building by gradually transforming its campus into a place, in transition towards social responsibility and sustainability and assumes fully its role in contributing to building more sustainable and just societies, where poverty would be eradicated, the planet protected and prosperity shared by all. An entire section of this commitment is dedicated to it on the University's website: <https://ueuromed.org/> and demonstrates the extent to which 15 of the 17 SDGs are monitored and updated annually.

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